

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEY IN BREAST CANCER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060080>

Relevance. The increase in the number of oncological diseases over the past decades requires the development of new drugs and methods of influencing tumor cells, in some cases, the intensification of chemotherapy regimens [1-2]. Along with the successes achieved in the treatment of tumor diseases, the toxicity of the treatment is quite a big problem. Kidney damage developing in cancer patients can lead to a change or increase in the concentration of drugs, thereby increasing their toxicity, prolonging the duration of hospitalization and increasing mortality [3].

The spectrum of kidney damage in tumor diseases is quite wide and can be caused both directly by tumor infiltration and damage to renal tissue by metabolites of tumor cells, glomerular lesion, and the nephrotoxic effect of drugs, radiation therapy. In addition, the risks associated with complications after bone marrow transplantation, infections due to immunosuppression (including sepsis), and tumor lysis syndrome should be taken into account [4]. Paclitaxel chemotherapeutic drugs are inhibitors of mitosis, block cell division, disrupt the function of microtubules and some enzyme proteins, as well as alter the metabolism of amino acids and some other substances, such as nucleic acids, lipid synthesis, and affect cellular respiration [2].

The aim of the work is to study the morphological and immunohistochemical characteristics of the kidney in breast cancer.

Materials and methods of research. The experiment was performed on 20 white female rats at the age of 3 months. All procedures for keeping rats and removing them from the experiment were carried out according to the rules of work using experimental animals.

As part of the work, experimental evidence of changes in kidney morphology was obtained. In breast cancer, a decrease in kidney mass and volume was observed in experimental animals subjected to chemotherapy, with the most informative indicators being the total area of the renal corpuscles, the area of the vascular tangle, the diameter of the proximal and distal convoluted tubules and their cavities. When comparing the parameters of the renal corpuscles of rats of the experimental groups with those of the control group after chemotherapy, the largest decrease in size was observed in rats of group 4 - by 1.81 times, and in the remaining groups - by 1.85 times.

References:

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